

Factors Contributing to Poor Performance of Learners in Mathematics at Primary Level: A Case of Selected Schools in Chirundu District of Lusaka Province, Zambia

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Abstract:

Mathematics education at the primary level plays a critical role in shaping students' academic trajectories and future opportunities. This study aimed to investigate factors contributing to poor performance of learners in mathematics at the primary level, focusing on three selected schools in the Chirundu district of Lusaka province in Zambia. The study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative methods within a descriptive survey design. A purposive and convenience sampling technique was utilized to select 150 participants, including educators and students, who provided insights into the research problem. Data was collected through questionnaires and interview guides, enabling a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. The quantitative data collected through the questionnaires were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods, such as descriptive statistics using SPSS and excel whereas the qualitative data from semi structured interviews were analyzed thematically. The findings revealed that factors such as teacher expertise, availability of teaching resources, and curriculum alignment significantly impacted students' mathematics performance. Additionally, the study highlighted the interconnectedness between student engagement, parental involvement, and the home environment in influencing mathematics outcomes. The research underscored the importance of addressing systemic challenges and implementing targeted interventions to enhance mathematics education at the primary level. Recommendations include investing in teacher training, improving resource allocation, and fostering partnerships between schools and communities to support student learning. Overall, this study contributed valuable insights into the complex dynamics of mathematics education, providing actionable recommendations for stakeholders to improve student outcomes in mathematics within the Chirundu District.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Mathematics Education, Parental involvement, Primary Level, and Teacher Expertise.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is universally recognized as a cornerstone of societal development, and within the realm of education, mathematics holds a pivotal role. Mathematics equips learners with essential problem-solving skills, logical reasoning abilities, and a strong foundation for advanced studies in various fields. Chanda & Mwila (2023) in their study noted that mathematics is a fundamental subject that plays a pivotal role in the academic development of learners, particularly at the primary level. The ability of primary school students to comprehend and excel in mathematics is not only indicative of their cognitive development but also contributes significantly to their overall academic success. Several factors contribute to the poor performance of learners in mathematics at the primary level. One significant issue is the lack of qualified and well-trained teachers who are proficient in teaching mathematical concepts effectively (Chilufya & Mulenga, 2015). This often leads to ineffective teaching methods that do not engage students or help them understand fundamental concepts.

Additionally, Chanda & Siyunda (2023) alluded that insufficient teaching and learning materials, such as textbooks and visual aids, further exacerbate the problem. Another contributing factor is the large class sizes in many primary schools, which limits the teacher's ability to provide individualized attention to struggling learners. Socio-economic factors, including poverty and lack of parental involvement, also play a role, as children from disadvantaged backgrounds often lack the necessary support at home to reinforce learning (Brown & Williams, 2018). Furthermore, many primary learners have negative attitudes towards mathematics, which can be linked to a lack of confidence or past failures, creating a cycle of underachievement. Lastly, language barriers, especially in contexts where the language of instruction is not the learner's first language, can hinder comprehension and problem-solving skills in mathematics. All these factors combined create a challenging environment for learners to perform well in mathematics at the primary level.

Primary education is the foundation of formal schooling, typically covering the early years of a child's education. In most systems, it begins with Grade 1 and continues through Grade 7 or 8, catering to children aged approximately six to twelve years. AU (2016) noted that the primary level is critical as it provides students with fundamental literacy, numeracy, and life skills that are essential for future learning and development. It also fosters the development of social, emotional, and cognitive abilities. In many regions, primary education is compulsory and is considered a basic right for all children, ensuring that they have the opportunity to acquire essential knowledge and skills. Curriculum content at this level often focuses on basic subjects such as mathematics, language arts, science, and social studies, with growing emphasis on integrating technology and fostering critical thinking skills (Mboози et al., 2024). Additionally, the primary level plays a key role in shaping students' attitudes toward learning, building their confidence, and preparing them for secondary education.

Mathematics education plays a critical role in developing students' logical reasoning, problem-solving skills, and analytical thinking, which are essential for success in various fields of study

and professional careers. Effective mathematics instruction helps students understand abstract concepts and apply them to real-world situations, fostering their ability to approach challenges systematically (Mwansa et al., 2019). However, mathematics education faces challenges such as a lack of qualified teachers, inadequate teaching materials, and the perception that math is difficult, which can lead to poor student engagement and performance. To improve outcomes, educators are increasingly adopting innovative teaching methods, including the integration of technology, collaborative learning, and differentiated instruction tailored to students' individual needs. This approach seeks to build students' confidence, deepen their understanding, and ultimately enhance their performance in mathematics, making it a fundamental aspect of their overall educational experience.

Chanda et al (2024a) says that academic performance refers to the measurable outcomes of a student's learning and achievement within an educational setting, often reflected through grades, test scores, and the completion of academic milestones. It is influenced by a variety of factors including the quality of teaching, availability of learning resources, student engagement, and personal motivation. External influences such as socio-economic background, parental involvement, and the availability of co-curricular activities also play critical roles. In the context of modern education, the integration of technology, the learning environment, and support structures within schools further contribute to shaping academic outcomes. Academic performance is not only a measure of individual capability but also a reflection of the effectiveness of the educational system as a whole, with a focus on how students acquire and apply knowledge in diverse subjects (Banda & Kafumbu, 2013).

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Despite efforts to improve the quality of education, the performance of learners in mathematics at the primary level in Chirundu district remains a significant concern. According to recent data from the Ministry of Education, there was a noticeable decline in mathematics scores among primary school students in the district, with an average drop of 15% over the past three years (MoE, 2022); (OECD, 2020). This decline was alarming, given the crucial role that a strong foundation in mathematics plays in shaping future academic and career opportunities for students. The need to identify and address the factors contributing to this decline was imperative to formulate effective interventions and enhance the overall educational outcomes in the selected schools.

1.3. Research Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

- Identify the key factors that underpinned poor performance in mathematics among primary school learners in selected primary schools of Chirundu district, Zambia.
- Evaluate curriculum-related issues that hinder the effective delivery of mathematics education in selected primary schools of Chirundu district, Zambia.

1.4. The Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine factors contributing to poor performance of learners in mathematics at primary level: a case of selected schools in Chirundu district of Lusaka province, Zambia.

1.5. Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by the Socioeconomic Status and Academic Achievement Theory. The theory posits that factors contributing to poor performance of learners in mathematics at the primary level are often linked to socioeconomic status (SES), which significantly impacts educational outcomes. Learners from low-income families frequently face challenges such as inadequate access to learning resources, including textbooks, tutoring, and digital tools, which are essential for grasping mathematical concepts. Additionally, Ngosa & Simukoko (2014) alluded that limited parental involvement and support in academic activities, often due to parents' lower educational backgrounds or time constraints, can hinder learners' progress. The quality of instruction in low SES areas may also be compromised by under-resourced schools and poorly trained teachers, leading to less effective teaching methods. Furthermore, learners from disadvantaged backgrounds may experience stress from financial instability, poor nutrition, or lack of a conducive learning environment at home, all of which contribute to reduced cognitive focus and academic achievement in mathematics. These factors combined often create a cycle of low performance that becomes difficult to break without targeted interventions (Williams & Brown, 2017).

1.6. Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in its potential to address a multifaceted educational challenge that extended beyond the boundaries of Chirundu district, Zambia, and resonated with broader international concerns. By comprehensively investigating the factors contributing to poor mathematics performance among primary school learners in Mandenga Zone, this study held the promise of yielding valuable insights with far-reaching implications. Firstly, it may inform evidence-based policy formulation and educational reforms at the district and national levels, facilitating the allocation of resources and the development of targeted interventions aimed at enhancing mathematics education. Secondly, this study may serve as a model for similar research endeavors in regions facing analogous educational issues, contributing to the global discourse on improving primary mathematics education. Furthermore, addressing the identified factors may not only elevate academic outcomes but also contribute to the socio-economic empowerment of learners, fostering a more prosperous future for the individuals and communities in Chirundu district. Ultimately, this study sought to bridge the knowledge gap regarding mathematics education disparities, aligning educational practices with the evolving needs of learners and society, and thereby advancing the cause of equitable and quality primary education.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a mixed-methods research design, combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing mathematics performance among primary school learners in Mandenga Zone, Chirundu District, Zambia. These methods were employed to gather rich, contextual insights into the experiences, perceptions, and attitudes of the participants regarding mathematics education. The study was conducted in Mandenga Zone, located within Chirundu District in Zambia. The total target population consisted of 1,500 individuals. The sample size for this study has been determined to be 150 individuals, which represents 10% of the total target population of 1500, comprising primary school pupils, administrators, teachers and parents within the selected schools in Mandenga Zone, Chirundu District, Zambia. To ensure a proportional representation of the various stakeholder groups within the primary education system, this sample size is distributed as follows: 2 school administrators from each school, 30 primary school pupils from each school, 10 primary school teachers from each school and 24 parents for pupils at the selected schools. To ensure that the sample accurately represented the target population and to enhance the reliability. The study utilized questionnaires and semi-structured interviews to collect data. For the quantitative data obtained through structured questionnaires, statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS software to generate descriptive statistics to come up with graphs and charts while for the qualitative data collected through in-depth interviews, thematic analysis was employed. The study upheld research ethical considerations such as voluntary participation of the respondents, anonymity, confidentiality, honesty, and right of privacy.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The following findings and discussions were presented according to set research objectives:

3.1. Key Factors that Underpinned Poor Performance in Mathematics among Primary School Learners

Data collected from the study revealed that overcrowded classrooms are a significant factor contributing to poor performance in mathematics among primary school learners. Mwanza & Sichula (2013) added that when classrooms are filled beyond their capacity, it becomes difficult for teachers to provide individualized attention and support to students, particularly those struggling with math concepts. The high student-to-teacher ratio means that teachers may not have enough time to assess each learner's understanding or address their specific needs, leading to a lack of clarity and confidence in mathematical problem-solving. Additionally, Chansa & Sakala (2017)'s study added that classroom management becomes more challenging, as maintaining discipline and keeping all students engaged in learning activities can be overwhelming in a crowded environment. This often results in disruptions that hinder effective teaching and learning. The lack of resources, such as textbooks and teaching aids, which must be shared among a large number of students, further exacerbates the problem. Overcrowded classrooms create an

environment where learners are less likely to participate actively, ask questions, or receive timely feedback, all of which are crucial for developing proficiency in mathematics (Muller & Schmidt, 2019). Consequently, this negatively impacts learners' academic performance and overall grasp of mathematical concepts.

The results further revealed that insufficient learning resources play a significant role in contributing to poor performance in mathematics among primary school learners, particularly in Zambia. Many schools, especially in rural and underserved areas, struggle with limited access to essential educational materials such as textbooks, teaching aids, and mathematical tools like calculators, geometric sets, or even simple manipulative used for hands-on learning (Chanda et al., 2024b). This scarcity hampers both the teaching and learning process, as teachers are often forced to rely on outdated or insufficient materials, while students are unable to engage with interactive and practical approaches to learning math. The lack of appropriate resources makes it difficult for learners to grasp foundational concepts, leading to a cumulative effect where students consistently fall behind in mathematical understanding. In Zambia, this challenge is further exacerbated by large class sizes, where individual attention is limited, and the few available resources are stretched thin. As a result, students are left at a disadvantage, ultimately affecting their overall performance in mathematics (Mwanza & Sichula, 2013).

Teachers noted that negative attitudes towards mathematics are a significant factor contributing to poor performance among primary school learners. Garcia (2020) explained that many students perceive mathematics as a difficult and intimidating subject, which fosters feelings of anxiety and frustration. This negative perception often stems from early struggles with basic concepts, leading to a lack of confidence in their ability to succeed in the subject. Such attitudes can be reinforced by external factors, including societal stereotypes that label mathematics as inherently challenging, particularly for certain groups such as girls (Smith & Johnson, 2019). One of the teachers expressed that:

“Learners often develop anxiety or a fear of mathematics, which negatively impacts their performance”.

Additionally, if learners face unsupportive learning environments, where teachers fail to make the subject engaging or accessible, their attitudes towards mathematics can worsen. The result is a disengagement from the subject, decreased motivation to put in the necessary effort, and ultimately lower achievement levels. This cycle of negativity can further perpetuate poor performance as learners become increasingly resistant to investing time and energy into improving their mathematical skills (Gonzalez & Lee, 2016).

School administrators explained that the lack of qualified teachers is a critical factor contributing to poor performance in mathematics among primary school learners. In many cases, teachers tasked with teaching mathematics may lack specialized training in the subject, resulting in insufficient mastery of mathematical concepts and ineffective instructional methods. This inadequacy hinders their ability to explain complex ideas, provide adequate problem-solving techniques, and address students' learning difficulties (Robinson, 2019). Furthermore, without the

proper pedagogical skills and confidence, these teachers often rely on rote memorization rather than fostering conceptual understanding, limiting students' ability to apply mathematics in real-world situations. The shortage of qualified teachers also leads to a high student-teacher ratio, reducing personalized attention and support for struggling learners (Lufupa et al., 2024). Consequently, this gap in teacher competency significantly impacts learners' confidence and interest in mathematics, ultimately resulting in lower performance outcomes.

The study also recorded that parental involvement plays a critical role in shaping the academic performance of primary school learners, particularly in subjects like mathematics. One of the learners stated that:

“Limited support from parents, especially in terms of helping with homework or reinforcing learning at home, can affect students' understanding and performance”.

Mbeba & Eidevall (2019) in their study observed that when parents are actively engaged in their children's education, they tend to provide necessary support, such as helping with homework, reinforcing concepts taught in school, and fostering a positive attitude towards learning. However, the lack of parental involvement has been identified as a key factor contributing to poor performance in mathematics among primary school learners. Many parents, due to low educational attainment, busy work schedules, or limited understanding of mathematical concepts, may struggle to assist their children effectively. This gap in support can lead to learners experiencing difficulties in grasping basic mathematical principles, ultimately leading to poor academic outcomes. Moreover, in homes where education is not prioritized or where parental expectations are low, children may lack the motivation to perform well academically (Chanda, 2024a). The absence of a structured learning environment at home further exacerbates these challenges, making it harder for learners to keep up with the curriculum, which results in persistent poor performance in mathematics.

Figure 1: Key Factors that Underpinned Poor Performance in Mathematics among Primary School Learners

3.2. Curriculum-Related Issues that Hinder the Effective Delivery of Mathematics Education

The study results showed that an overloaded curriculum is a significant curriculum-related issue that hinders the effective delivery of mathematics education, particularly at the primary school level. Chanda (2024b)'s study recorded that when the curriculum is packed with numerous subjects and topics, educators are often forced to teach at a fast pace to cover all the required content within a limited timeframe. This rushed approach leaves little room for deep understanding and mastery of mathematical concepts, as teachers may not have enough time to focus on key areas or address individual student difficulties. Students, on the other hand, struggle to keep up with the extensive and often disconnected topics, leading to confusion and superficial learning. The lack of opportunity for reinforcement, practice, and real-life application of mathematical concepts further weakens students' grasp of the subject (Chingosho & Chawanzwa, 2018). Additionally, the pressure to meet curriculum requirements may cause teachers to prioritize quantity over quality, reducing their ability to employ interactive and engaging teaching

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methods that could enhance mathematical understanding. Ultimately, an overloaded curriculum limits both students' ability to build a solid foundation in mathematics and teachers' capacity to provide meaningful, effective instruction.

Respondents alluded that lack of relevance to real-life applications is a significant curriculum-related issue that hinders the effective delivery of mathematics education. When mathematical concepts and skills are perceived as abstract and disconnected from students' everyday experiences, engagement and understanding can suffer. Chanda (2024c) supported this finding by stating that this disconnect often results from curricula that focus heavily on theoretical aspects without adequately demonstrating how these concepts apply in practical, real-world contexts. For instance, students might struggle to see the value of algebraic equations or geometric formulas if they do not encounter problems that illustrate their practical use in daily life or in future careers. Rogoff (2003) says that this lack of relevance can lead to diminished motivation, reduced effort, and lower achievement, as students may question the purpose of learning material that seems irrelevant to their lives. To address this issue, curricula need to incorporate real-life scenarios, practical applications, and interdisciplinary approaches that show students how mathematics is used in various professions, technologies, and everyday problem-solving (James, 2020). By bridging the gap between theory and practice, educators can enhance students' appreciation of mathematics, improve their engagement, and ultimately foster a deeper and more lasting understanding of the subject.

Additionally, inadequate progression of concepts within the curriculum can significantly hinder the effective delivery of mathematics education, particularly at the primary school level. One of the teachers pointed out that:

“Poor sequencing of mathematical concepts within the curriculum can create gaps in student understanding. If foundational concepts are not mastered before moving on to more advanced topics, students may struggle to keep up”.

This issue arises when mathematical concepts are not sequenced in a logical, coherent manner, leading to gaps in students' understanding and difficulties in building on prior knowledge. When mathematical topics are introduced without a clear progression from simple to complex, students may struggle to grasp fundamental concepts, which impedes their ability to comprehend more advanced material. For instance, if foundational arithmetic skills are not firmly established before advancing to more complex operations like fractions or algebra, students may find themselves unable to apply these skills effectively. This lack of a structured progression can also result in cognitive overload, where students are presented with concepts that are too advanced for their current level of understanding (Johnson, 2019). Consequently, the lack of coherent progression not only affects students' immediate learning outcomes but can also have long-term implications, as they may struggle with future mathematics content and develop a negative attitude towards the subject. Addressing this issue requires a well-designed curriculum that ensures each concept builds upon previous knowledge, incorporates regular review and reinforcement, and is tailored to the developmental stages of learners to promote a solid foundation in mathematics.

The study further noted that insufficient integration of technology in mathematics education poses a significant challenge to the effective delivery of the subject, impacting both teaching and learning processes. Chanda et al (2024c) added that the lack of technological resources, such as interactive whiteboards, educational software, and digital tools, limits educators' ability to employ innovative teaching methods that can enhance student engagement and understanding. Without these resources, teachers may rely heavily on traditional teaching methods, which can be less effective in addressing diverse learning styles and needs. Additionally, the absence of technology integration restricts students' exposure to digital tools that are increasingly relevant in modern mathematics practices and problem-solving. Zohaib et al (2024) in their study revealed that this gap not only hampers students' ability to develop essential digital skills but also undermines their readiness for technology-driven careers. Moreover, insufficient integration of technology can result in missed opportunities for personalized learning, where adaptive learning platforms could provide tailored instruction and immediate feedback based on individual student performance. The overall effect is a diminished capacity to make mathematics education more interactive, engaging, and aligned with contemporary educational standards, ultimately hindering students' academic achievement and interest in the subject (Yelland, 2005).

Further, inadequate teacher preparation stands as a significant curriculum-related issue that undermines the effective delivery of mathematics education. One of the administrators explained that:

“Teachers who lack comprehensive training in both mathematical content and pedagogical strategies often struggle to convey complex concepts clearly and engagingly”.

Schmidt (2017) says that insufficient preparation can lead to a lack of confidence in teaching various mathematical topics, resulting in a reliance on rote learning rather than fostering deep understanding and critical thinking. This issue is compounded when teachers are not equipped with up-to-date resources or effective instructional techniques, which can diminish their ability to address diverse student needs and adapt to different learning styles. Additionally, inadequate preparation may result in a limited understanding of curriculum standards and assessment practices, further impairing the ability to design effective lesson plans and evaluate student progress accurately. As a consequence, students may experience gaps in their mathematical knowledge, struggle with foundational concepts, and ultimately perform poorly in mathematics. Addressing this issue requires a systemic approach to improve teacher education programs, ongoing professional development, and the provision of adequate teaching resources to enhance the overall quality of mathematics instruction (Alma et al., 2024).

Parents noted that an inflexible curriculum is a significant barrier to effective mathematics education, as it fails to accommodate the diverse learning needs and paces of students. A rigid curriculum often adheres to a fixed sequence of topics and teaching methods, which may not align with the varying abilities and interests of learners (Ajibola & Oyeniya, 2017). This inflexibility limits teachers' ability to adapt their instruction based on formative assessments, preventing them from addressing individual learning gaps and adjusting content to better suit students' needs.

Consequently, students who struggle with certain mathematical concepts may fall further behind, while those who grasp the material quickly may become disengaged due to a lack of challenge. Additionally, an inflexible curriculum can stifle teachers' creativity and pedagogical innovation, as they are confined to prescribed materials and methods, reducing their capacity to employ diverse teaching strategies or integrate real-world applications. This rigidity ultimately hampers the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills, as it emphasizes rote learning over deeper understanding and application of the subject concepts (Chanda, 2024d). Thus, an inflexible curriculum not only undermines the effectiveness of mathematics education but also contributes to inequitable learning experiences, adversely affecting student outcomes and engagement.

The respondents further said that misalignment with student needs is a significant curriculum-related issue that hinders the effective delivery of mathematics education. Adekola & Akinboboye (2017) in their study noted that when the mathematics curriculum does not align with the diverse needs and learning styles of students, it creates a gap between what is taught and what students are capable of understanding and applying. This misalignment can manifest in various ways, such as a one-size-fits-all approach that does not account for different levels of prior knowledge, learning speeds, and cognitive abilities. For instance, a curriculum that assumes all students have the same level of mathematical understanding may fail to provide adequate support for those who struggle with foundational concepts, while also not sufficiently challenging more advanced learners (Anderson, 2019). Additionally, if the curriculum does not incorporate relevant real-world applications or contexts that resonate with students' interests and experiences, it can lead to disengagement and a lack of motivation. This disconnect between the curriculum and student needs often results in lower academic performance, increased frustration, and diminished confidence in mathematics. To address this issue, it is essential to design and implement curricula that are flexible and adaptable, incorporate differentiated instruction strategies, and regularly assess and adjust the curriculum based on student feedback and performance data (Chanda, 2024e). This approach ensures that the curriculum is responsive to the varied needs of students and supports their overall learning and achievement in mathematics.

Figure 2: Curriculum-Related Issues That Hinder the Effective Delivery of Mathematics Education

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the factors contributing to poor performance in mathematics among primary school learners in Chirundu District are multifaceted and interrelated. Key issues include the inadequacy of instructional resources and materials, which hampers the ability of both teachers and students to engage effectively with mathematical concepts. Overcrowded classrooms exacerbate this problem by limiting individual attention and support for each student. Additionally, a lack of qualified mathematics teachers impedes the quality of instruction, leading to gaps in foundational knowledge. Socioeconomic factors, such as poverty and limited access to supplementary educational support, further hinder students' academic progress. Furthermore, inadequate parental involvement and support in the learning process also play a crucial role, as they affect students' motivation and engagement. These factors combined create a challenging educational environment that significantly impacts learners' performance in mathematics, necessitating comprehensive interventions to address these issues and enhance educational outcomes in the district.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are actions that should be taken on the basis of the findings of this study:

1. Enhanced Teacher Training and Support:

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- The ministry of education through teacher training institutions should implement continuous professional development programs focused on modern teaching methodologies, particularly in mathematics.
- 2. Improved Learning Resources and Infrastructure:**
 - The ministry of education should invest in upgrading the learning environment and providing adequate resources to support mathematics education.
- 3. Engagement with Parents and the Community:**
 - The ministry of education through DEBS offices should foster stronger partnerships between schools, parents, and the community to support students' learning in mathematics.

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